

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300
Sacramento, CA 95814

September 8, 2022

In Reply Refer to:
2022-0002492-S7-001

Frances Malamud-Roam
Regulatory Division Project Manager
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
San Francisco District
450 Golden Gate Avenue
San Francisco, California 94102

Subject: Formal consultation for the 900 Innes Park Redevelopment Project (Corps File No. SPK-2016-00417S), City and County of San Francisco, California.

Dear Ms. Malamud-Roam:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps) November 2, 2021 request for initiation of informal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the proposed 900 Innes Park Redevelopment Project (project) in the City and County of San Francisco, California. Your electronic mail (email) request was received by the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office on November 2, 2021. The Corps sent a subsequent email on April 29, 2022, to notify the Service that the Corps changed its initial determination and request formal consultation. In the April 29, 2022, email the Corps determined that the project may affect, and is likely to adversely affect endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*)(CCR). This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

In considering your request, we based our evaluation on the following: (1) the Corps' November 2, 2021, letter requesting informal consultation; (2) the Corps' April 29, 2022, email with the change in determination and request for formal consultation; (3) the March 2021 *San Francisco Recreation and Parks Department 900 Innes Redevelopment Project Biological Assessment* (BA) prepared by Anchor QEA (consultant) and the revised version received by the Service on April 21, 2022; (4) emails between the Corps, the Service, and the consultant for the project; and (5) other information available to the Service.

Recent genetic analyses of rail species resulted in a change in the common name and taxonomy of the large, “clapper-type” rails (*Rallus longirostris*) of the west coast of North America to Ridgway’s rail (*Rallus obsoletus*) (Maley and Brumfield 2013; Chesser *et al.* 2014). Thus the California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) is now referred to in the scientific community as the California Ridgway’s rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*). The change in the common name and taxonomy of the California clapper rail, however, does not change the listing status of the species under the Act and will be referred to by the original name in this document.

CONSULTATION HISTORY

November 2, 2021	The Service received the informal consultation request from the Corps.
October 2021 - March 2022	The Service conducted various telephone phone and email conversations providing technical assistance and requests for further information, specifically regarding effects of the pile driving portion of the project.
April 21, 2022	The consultant sent the Service an updated BA that addressed pile driving effects to CCR.
April 29, 2022	The Corps sent the Service an email changing their effects determination and requesting formal consultation.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The San Francisco Recreation and Parks Department (RPD) is redeveloping the 900 Innes Avenue (900 Innes) site in San Francisco’s Bayview-Hunters Point neighborhood. The proposed project entails in-water and upland improvements to establish a public park that provides shoreline access and amenities at 900 Innes. The project involves the construction of a variety of amenities and improvements. In-water components include two new piers, a floating dock, gangway structures that would replace dilapidated piers that previously provided private San Francisco Bay (Bay) access, and a “Shop Building”. Timing of the project would depend on funding. Minimum timeframe for completion would likely be approximately 2 years, but could take as long as 5 years. For the purposes of this consultation, the Service has focused on the construction of the piers, the “Shop Building”, and other in-water work that will use pile-driving techniques and has summarized those project components below. Please refer to the BA for a comprehensive project description with both the wetland and upland components.

Boatyard piers that have been previously removed would be reintroduced through two elevated, pile-supported pier structures. Pier 1 would consist of a 35-foot by 40-foot concrete deck extending into the water over the mudflats perpendicular to the shoreline in an easterly direction. Pier 1 would occupy approximately 1,400 square feet (sf) and require approximately sixteen 20-inch concrete piles to support the decking. Pier 2 would be located southeast of Pier 1 and would

also extend into the water over the mudflats perpendicular to the shoreline. It would consist of a 102-foot by 47-foot concrete deck over a total area of 4,794 sf, supported by thirty-six 20-inch concrete piles.

A pile-supported ramp would be constructed on the eastern side of Pier 2, providing a landside connection to the proposed gangway and pile-supported floating dock. The pile-supported ramp would consist of a 40-foot by 12.6-foot sloped concrete deck over a total area of 504 sf, supported by four 20-inch concrete piles.

A floating dock would be installed and connected via a clear span gangway to the pile-supported ramp. The floating dock would measure approximately 80 feet by 12 feet over a total area of 960 sf and would be supported by five 16-inch concrete piles.

The “Shop Building” would be situated above the king tide 2,100 flood elevation and the building foundation would consist of a concrete slab-on-grade with a retaining wall on the west, north, and east sides. Twenty-three 24-inch-diameter concrete piles will be installed more than 30 feet above mean high water (MHW) elevation to support the retaining wall for this building, and three 20-inch concrete piles will be installed more than 30 feet above the MHW elevation to support the stairs.

Due to the City of San Francisco (City) ordinance on noise restrictions, pile-driving activities would be restricted to between 7:00 a.m. and 8:00 p.m. Monday through Friday unless pre-approved by RPD for additional days and/or hours. Eighty-seven 16- to 24-inch concrete piles and eighty-eight 8-inch helical piles would be driven with a vibratory or impact hammer, depending on site geotechnical conditions. Pile driving is estimated to take 20-24 weeks over 2 seasons.

Conservation Measures

The RPD proposes to conduct all pile driving from September 1 to January 31 to avoid impacts to nesting CCR. The proposed project would also include use of cushion blocks to reduce noise levels during impact hammer use.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action.” The project site lies on the eastern shore of the San Francisco Peninsula within the Bayview-Hunters Point neighborhood in the southeast quadrant of the City of San Francisco. It is generally bounded to the northwest by India Basin Shoreline Park, to the east by an extension of the Bay and India Basin Open Space, to the southwest by Innes Avenue, and to the southeast by the Griffith Street right-of-way. The Action Area includes approximately 10 acres of tidal marsh habitat in Heron’s Head Park that could support CCR. For the purpose of this biological opinion and to identify areas of potential behavioral effects to CCR in Heron’s Head Park, the Action Area was calculated to include any tidal marsh habitat at Heron’s Head Park located in a zone that was based on 150 decibel (dB) root mean square (RMS) threshold and a sound attenuation to ambient

background levels at Heron's Head Park of approximately 53 A-weighted decibels (dBA) at a radius of approximately 12,500 feet.

ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK for the JEOPARDY DETERMINATION

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. "Jeopardize the continued existence of" means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the range wide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current range wide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of the Species

CCR

Information about the CCR biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the California clapper rail 5-year Review, available at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3088.pdf (Service 2020). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat being the most significant effect.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The environmental baseline includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the

anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

The project site is primarily dense urban development with open space consisting of man-made parks. Heron's Head Park is located across the open water of India Basin and consists of a mix of open space uplands that transitions into a saltwater tidal marsh.

CCR are year-round residents of the tidal wetlands of the Bay estuaries; however, no rails are known to nest within or adjacent to the actual project footprint. The project area does have what could be considered fragmented foraging habitat for CCR within vegetated shorelines nearby; however, these areas are disturbed, patchy, disconnected, and at high tide, vegetative cover is limited, providing minimal protection from predators. It is unlikely that CCR would be present in these areas. The closest documented breeding or attempted breeding sites are associated with Heron's Head Park, which is approximately 1,600 feet north of the project area. CCR were documented at Heron's Head Park during the breeding season in 2010 and 2011 (Fimrite 2011; McBroom *et al.* 2011). This species has occurred intermittently since then, with a recent 2018 sighting at Heron's Head Park (Ebird 2018). However, the Invasive Spartina Project annual rail surveys did not identify any CCR during the breeding seasons in 2018, 2019, or 2020 at this location (Olofson Environmental 2018, 2020, 2021).

The Service consulted on the India Basin 900 Innes Avenue Remediation Project (Service File No. 08FBDT00-2019-I-0290) dated October 29, 2019, for debris and contaminated soil removal, and concurred with a not likely to adversely affect determination for the CCR.

Effects of the Proposed Action

Effects of the action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

For the purpose of this consultation, the Service is not considering the upland elements of the project within the 900 Innes Road project area as those elements are not expected to have any adverse effects to the CCR or its habitat. No CCR are expected to be within the project area and there is little to no habitat that would support the CCR nearby. The Service is instead focusing on the construction of the piers, the "Shop Building", and other in-water work that will use pile-driving techniques that could create adverse noise effects to the nearest known nesting occurrences of CCR at Heron's Head Park approximately 1,600 feet northeast from where construction equipment would operate.

CCR

CCR are not anticipated to be within the immediate construction footprint of the project because the habitat within the construction footprint is considered to be unsuitable or marginal. The proposed project will likely generate temporary noise and visual disturbance that will exceed ambient conditions in tidal marsh habitats at Heron's Head Park that likely support CCR year-round. Pile driving noise and vibration may interfere with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Intolerable levels of disturbance that may force individual CCR to flush from cover or prevent them from seeking available cover that could expose them to a predation risk that otherwise would not occur. Pile driving outside of the CCR breeding season will avoid effects to breeding CCRs, eggs, and chicks.

Based on noise studies, airborne sound from a single source (i.e., a "point" source) radiates uniformly outward in a spherical pattern as it travels away from the source. The sound level attenuates at a rate of 6 A-weighted decibels (dBA) for each doubling of distance. For example, the airborne source noise level from pile driving using an impact pile hammer (the noisiest equipment for the project) was assumed to be 101 dBA based on the published noise emission level for impact pile driving at a distance of 50 feet (Federal Highway Administration 2006). The noise reduces 6 dBA for each doubling of distance; therefore, it would be 95 dBA at 100 feet, 89 at 200 feet, 83 dBA at 400 feet, 77 dBA at 800 feet, 71 dBA at 1,600 feet, 65 dBA at 3,200 feet, 59 dBA at 6,400 feet, and 53 dBA at 12,800 feet. The daytime airborne ambient noise level was assumed to be 53.1 dBA based on daytime measurements collected at India Basin, another park close to Heron's Head Park, and noted that vehicular traffic on local roadways is the primary contributor to the current ambient noise environment in the vicinity (City 2018). Based on these data and applying a noise dissipation rate of 6 dBA per doubling of distance, the noise from an impact or vibratory pile driver operating at the project site would attenuate below a conservative background ambient noise level of 53.1 dB at a distance no greater than approximately 12,416 feet. The Service has estimated these noise levels at this distance will disturb CCR within the approximately 10 acres of Heron's Head Park. All other construction activities are anticipated to generate noise that does not extend 1,600 feet, so they would be unlikely to affect birds at Heron's Head Park. Use of the impact or vibratory pile hammer would be limited to the approximate 20-24 weeks duration of pile driving outside of the CCR breeding season.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local, or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions that are unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section; they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species*, the *Environmental Baseline*, the *Effects of the Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that the proposed 900 Innes Park Redevelopment Project is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the CCR.

This is based on the current status and distribution of the CCR population range-wide, lack of suitable habitat on the project site, and implementation of the *Conservation Measures* to minimize the adverse effects on individual CCR and their habitat during construction activities such as limiting noise effects outside of the CCR breeding season. The project will also not create any physical disturbance that would result in the loss or degradation of available suitable habitat nearby.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harm in the definition of “take” in the Act means an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Such [an] act may include significant habitat modification or degradation where it actually kills or injures wildlife by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering (50 CFR 17.3). Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not the purpose of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the proposed protective measures and the terms and conditions of an incidental take statement and occurs as a result of the action as proposed.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

CCR

The Service anticipates incidental take of CCR will be difficult to detect or quantify because of their inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy in tidal marsh habitats resulting in low detectability. Therefore, the Service anticipates incidental take of all CCR within the approximate 10 acres of tidal marsh habitat at Heron’s Head Park in the form of harm from the impairment of essential behaviors through the noise effects of pile driving. Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measure, take in the form of harm from impairing essential behaviors within the 10-acre portion of the Action Area will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act. The Service does not anticipate that take in the form of wounding or killing of CCR during construction will occur due to the nature of the project and implementation of the proposed

Conservation Measures. Therefore, the Service is not exempting take in the form of wound or kill for any CCR during construction activities from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that this level of anticipated take is not likely to result in jeopardy to the CCR.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

The Service has determined that the following Reasonable and Prudent Measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the effects of the 900 Innes Park Redevelopment Project on the species:

1. Adverse effects to the CCR shall be minimized to the fullest extent possible.

Term and Condition

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall comply with the following Term and Condition, which implement the Reasonable and Prudent Measure described above. This Term and Condition is nondiscretionary. The following Term and Condition implements the Reasonable and Prudent Measure:

1. The project proponent shall fully implement the proposed project, including the conservation measures, guidelines, implementing procedure, the Reasonable and Prudent Measure, and the corresponding Term and Condition as described in this biological opinion.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, the Corps shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. Injured listed species shall be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person. Notification will be made to the contact below in *Reporting Requirements*, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the *Disposition of Individuals Taken* section below.

2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and California Natural Diversity Database (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/CNDDDB/Submitting-Data>).

Disposition of Individuals Taken

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as a Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the species was found, the location where it was found, the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is Jana Affonso, Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

1. Participate in recovery planning and implementation of conservation actions consistent with recovery planning documents.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION—CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes informal consultation on the 900 Innes Park Redevelopment Project. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16,

- (a) Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:
 - (1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;

- (2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
 - (3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or
 - (4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.
- (b) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:
- (1) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
 - (2) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response to Brian Hansen, Senior Fish and Wildlife Biologist, at Brian_Hansen@fws.gov or (916) 930-5642 or Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager, at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to Service file number 2022-0002492-S7-001 in any future correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

Donald Ratcliff
Field Supervisor

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